

Introduction to Machine Learning: Concepts, Algorithms, and Practical Applications

Ricardo Murer

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4996-3793>

Affiliation: SKF | IBMEC | Series: Artificial Intelligence | Foundations

Head of AI Enablement - SKF and Visiting Professor of AI - IBMEC

rdmurer@gmail.com | @rdmurer

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Abstract

We live in the era of Big Data, where massive volumes of information are generated every second. One of the most transformative subareas of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that has emerged from reading, analyzing, and identifying complex patterns in data is Machine Learning. In this article, I present a brief historical context of the field, exploring its evolution from the first algorithms to modern architectures. Then, I examine the fundamental concepts that underpin the field, including the main paradigms and algorithms of supervised and unsupervised learning, as well as their practical applications. I also discuss the emergence of synthetic data as an innovative strategy to overcome limitations in the availability and quality of real data, in addition to its ethical and technical implications.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, machine learning, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning, synthetic data, decision trees, support vector machines

Introduction

Machine Learning is not something new, and its origins date back to the 1950s, with Arthur Samuel, an American computer scientist and electrical engineer who coined the term "Machine Learning" in 1959. Samuel, who worked at IBM, developed a program capable of playing checkers and improving its performance through experience. Samuel defined Machine Learning as the "field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed." Although the concept was formalized by Samuel, the theoretical roots trace back to earlier works, such as Frank Rosenblatt's perceptron in 1957 and even Alan

Turing's studies on machine intelligence in the 1950s. (Murer, 2024a)

Samuel's revolutionary vision, however, was that instead of programming all possible rules to solve a problem, computers could discover these rules on their own by analyzing data and finding patterns. This paradigm shift, *from explicit programming to data-driven learning*, can be considered the conceptual foundation that supports the entire field of Machine Learning to this day.

According to Alpaydin, "the goal of machine learning is to program computers to use example data or past experience to solve a given problem." (Alpaydin, 2020)

Types of Machine Learning

There are four main types of Machine Learning algorithms: supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforcement.

Each has specific characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses, being suitable for solving different categories of problems. For didactic purposes and considering the prevalence in current applications, I will detail the three fundamental types: Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, and Reinforcement Learning. Observe Figure 1.

its movies and TV shows using various criteria, such as genre, actors, release date, and keywords that appear in the plot. This is essential for Netflix to make more accurate recommendations to its users and personalize the experience.

• Supervised Learning

In this type of Machine Learning, the algorithm is trained with a labeled dataset, that is, data that has already been marked with one or more properties or characteristics. The input data and the corresponding output values are known, and the algorithm learns to map the input data to

Figure 1 – Classic Machine Learning

• Unsupervised Learning

In this case, the Machine Learning algorithm is trained on an unlabeled dataset, where the output values are unknown. The algorithm learns to find patterns and structures in the input data. After the algorithm is trained, it can be used to discover hidden relationships and structures in the data. Netflix uses "clustering" to categorize

the correct output values with the help of the labels. After the algorithm is trained, it can be used to make predictions about new data that do not have labels. For example, a supervised learning algorithm can be trained on a dataset of images and their corresponding labels (e.g., cats, dogs, tigers) and then used to classify new

images of these animals. In this type of learning, we have two subcategories:

- Classification:** In classification tasks, the Machine Learning program must draw a conclusion from observed values and determine which category new observations belong to. For example, they are used in health diagnosis by classifying patient records into categories such as healthy or sick, based on symptoms and exam history. Another example is customer segmentation, done by marketing areas where this type of algorithm allows classifying customers into categories such as high value, medium, or low value, considering their demographic, behavioral, or past purchase characteristics.

- Regression:** In regression tasks, the Machine Learning program must estimate the relationships between variables and predict a continuous output variable. More practically, regression will return a number. For example, it is used to predict the temperature at a specific time of day based on historical temperature data. Another example: given a person's photograph, predict their age. Note that in both cases, the prediction was a number.

- Reinforcement Learning**

According to Sutton & Barto (Sutton & Barto, 2015), Reinforcement Learning is a computational approach to learning from interaction with an environment aimed at achieving a goal. In this process, an agent observes the state of the environment, selects and executes actions, receives rewards, and learns which policy (decision strategy) maximizes the cumulative reward over time. Observe Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Reinforcement Learning

It is characterized by three main aspects:

1. Closed-loop nature: The actions of the learning system influence its subsequent inputs and the situations it encounters.
2. Trial-and-error learning: The learner is not told which actions to take but must discover which actions yield the most reward by trying them.
3. Delayed consequences: Actions can affect not only the immediate reward but also subsequent situations and all future rewards.

Main Algorithms

Within each type of Machine Learning, there are specific algorithms that are widely used in practice. The decision to adopt one algorithm or another is complex, as it depends on different factors, such as: the objective of the problem and the business context, the nature, quality, and volume of available data, the available computational resources, the level of interpretability required, and the expected performance metrics for the specific problem.

It is also common to test multiple algorithms for the same use case or problem, in order to compare performance in terms of response time and accuracy of results.

Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman (2009) and James et al. (2013) provide a comprehensive

approach to Machine Learning algorithms. Below, I present the six most relevant algorithms, objectively, with practical application examples.

1. Decision Tree - Supervised

Decision Trees are algorithms that create a decision model based on a hierarchical structure similar to a flowchart, where each internal node represents a test on an attribute, each branch represents the outcome of the test, and each leaf represents a class decision or value. This algorithm is highly interpretable and intuitive.

Practical example: A real estate agency uses decision trees to prioritize sales leads, integrating variables such as customer budget, location, historical engagement, and company size. The model generates interpretable rules, such as "If budget > US\$ 50,000 and high engagement and premium location, then prioritize closing the deal."

2. Logistic Regression - Supervised

Despite the name containing "regression", Logistic Regression is a classification algorithm that estimates the probability of an instance belonging to a particular class, using a logistic function to map predictions to values between 0 and 1. It is especially effective for binary classification problems. **Practical example:** E-commerce companies use logistic regression to predict whether a customer will make a purchase (yes/no) based on variables such as time on site, number of pages visited, previous purchase history, and traffic source.

3. Random Forest - Supervised

Random Forest is an ensemble learning algorithm that builds multiple decision trees during training and combines their predictions to produce a more robust and accurate result. This method reduces the overfitting problem common in individual decision trees. **Practical**

example: Insurance companies use random forests to predict vehicle claim risk, analyzing multiple variables such as driver age, car model, accident history, region of use, and annual mileage, generating a more accurate risk score.

Overfitting - Occurs when a model learns the details and noise in the training data too well, showing excellent performance on that data but poor performance when applied to new data, losing the ability to generalize.

4. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) - Supervised

The KNN algorithm has existed since the 1950s and 1960s and was well known in the scientific research area. It classifies new data based on similarity with training data, identifying the K nearest neighbors in the feature space and assigning the most common class among them. It is a simple algorithm but can be computationally expensive on large datasets. **Practical example:** Streaming services such as Netflix and Spotify use KNN for recommendation systems, identifying users with similar tastes (close neighbors) and suggesting movies, series, or songs that these users with similar profiles also liked.

5. Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Supervised

SVM is a powerful algorithm. Simply put, it works as if it draws a **line (or boundary)** that divides the data into different groups, choosing the safest possible separation—the one that leaves the greatest distance between the groups. This helps the model make more accurate predictions, even when the data is complex. It is particularly effective in high-dimensional spaces and when the number of dimensions exceeds the number of samples. **Practical example:** In skin cancer diagnosis systems, an SVM can be used to analyze images of skin lesions and classify them as benign or malignant. For this, the model evaluates features extracted from the images,

such as color, texture, edges, and shape of the lesion, helping doctors make more accurate decisions, even when the data is complex.

6. K-Means (K-Means Clustering) - Unsupervised

K-Means is a clustering algorithm that partitions the data into K distinct groups (clusters), where each observation belongs to the cluster with the closest mean. The algorithm iteratively assigns points to clusters and recalculates centroids until convergence. **Practical example:** Retail networks use K-Means for customer segmentation, grouping them into distinct profiles (such as "high-value frequent shoppers", "occasional shoppers", "promotion hunters") based on purchasing behavior patterns, allowing personalized marketing strategies for each segment.

Synthetic Data

Collecting data from the physical world can be expensive, time-consuming, prone to errors, biases, and various legal restrictions. The use of internet data for training models has also become increasingly complex, as regulatory bodies impose stricter norms to protect user privacy and sensitive data, such as faces, license plates, medical records, and other identifiable information. These limitations have made data one of the main bottlenecks of modern Machine Learning, directly impacting the ability to scale, generalize, and validate AI models safely and reliably.

To overcome these challenges, AI companies have resorted to the use of synthetic data, that is, information artificially generated in controlled environments to train AI algorithms. In the context of Machine Learning, synthetic data plays a strategic role by enabling large-scale experimentation, accelerating development cycles, and allowing model training in rare, extreme, or ethically sensitive scenarios that

would hardly be obtainable in the real world. These data allow eliminating the aforementioned problems, in addition to avoiding class imbalance, when certain categories appear infrequently in real data, and labeling errors, which can compromise training quality by introducing noise or inaccuracy in the responses of AI models. (Murer, 2025)

Conclusion

Machine Learning represents one of the most significant technological transformations of recent decades, establishing itself as a fundamental pillar of modern AI. From its conception by Arthur Samuel in the 1950s to current applications and services, there has been an extraordinary evolution, with applications in different areas as presented in the "practical examples". Throughout this article, we explored the three fundamental paradigms of Machine Learning: supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement, and we also saw how the choice among different algorithms, from Decision Trees to Deep Neural Networks. The arrival of synthetic data represents an innovative response to the challenges of scarcity, quality, and bias in real data, opening new possibilities for training more robust models, even being fundamental for training robots. However, this evolution also confronts us with important ethical and technical questions that demand continuous reflection.

The future of Machine Learning lies in the pursuit of more disruptive models: more energy-efficient, algorithms capable of learning with less data, systems that explain their decisions transparently and are capable of self-assessing their data sources before using them, not propagating bias or misinformation.

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About the Author

Ricardo Murer is Head of AI at SKF and Visiting Professor of AI at IBMEC university. Graduated in Computer Science (USP) and with a master's in Communication (USP), he is certified by MIT in Innovation and Generative AI, as well as in Ethics by the University of Oxford. Author of two books on Artificial Intelligence: "Fundamentos da Inteligência Artificial" and "A Máquina Final", he

is also a member of the Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AAAI).

Instagram: @rdmurer

Website: <https://www.rdmurer.com.br>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4996-3793>